
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND THE NEW APPROACHES IN TOURISM

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The last decade has seen major changes in the travel distribution landscape. First, the Internet began a revolution and dramatically changed the way the tourism industry works. The spreading of smartphones and social media has created further both chaos and new opportunities. While opening up new opportunities for growth, these developments also created new operational challenges. Hoteliers and other business leaders operating in the travel industry have needed to follow the latest digital trends. Failure to do so can result in competitors gaining a competitive advantage.

The economics and structure of the tourism industry have changed dramatically with the advent of digitalization and digital technology. These developments have facilitated business transparency, pricing and competition, cost optimization and increased production efficiency. Indeed, the tourism industry has become the largest category of services sold over the Internet.

The possibilities of digital solutions allow the formation of many new attractive and interesting tours. The incorporation of technologies into urban settings stimulates the demand for tourist destinations, consequently enhancing the potential of the tourism industry. The advent of digital technologies is revolutionizing the format of the tourist sector. The capacity to communicate in any language, enabled by rapid translation technology, is an illustrative example.

It should be noted that one of the modern digital technological achievements is the ability to encode the perception of reality. Individuals with disabilities, constrained by their inability to travel, frequently experience feelings of inferiority and isolation from the broader world, which can ultimately lead to depression. Virtual travel offers a potential solution to this problem.

Essentially, in many respects, both in terms of physical perception and socio-psychological characteristics, the realm of virtual travel fails to meet the expectations of tourists. Many experts and analysts believe that the future of virtual tourism is about to change dramatically with the advent of digital technology, enabling people, families and friends to take extensive virtual tours that provide the same kind of experience they would get from traveling in person.

As a result of the digitalization of the tourism industry and the decrease in profits of specialized tourist organizations, the number of people who prefer to create their own travel route, buy air tickets, book hotels, etc. is constantly increasing.

In the past, the problem of booking and purchasing online at various services providing transport services was the professional construction of the route with the connection of the entire flight, but with the emergence of "big data" and the introduction of artificial intelligence, it is possible to structure the entire trip in a few actions.

On the basis of the research carried out on the website of the travel agency book.com, we found out that the majority of tourists would like to be assisted by a real person or a chatbot, and the number of such tourists is approximately 50 %. Chatbots can be a substitute for live communication with an advisor, and are capable of answering a wide range of questions from users, such as Kayak or Alice.

They provide recommendations and advice to the traveler, from buying airfares, to considering the budget available to the user, to recommending tourist attractions in the desired places.

Digital transformation allows for desk-based marketing research on the potential customer:

- data about a person's profile becomes available,
- the places he prefers,
- the amount of time he or she spends at a given location, etc.
- the application of digital technology has the effect of reducing the cost of surveys,
- the system enables the segmentation of customer types, thereby facilitating the adaptation of tourist offerings to align with evolving customer interests.

According to the World Economic Forum's Digital Transformation Initiative (DTI), digitizing the aviation, tourism, and hospitality industries could add \$305 billion to the economy through increased industry profitability. There is a potential for \$700 billion in benefits to come. There is a potential for \$700 billion in benefits to customers and society as a whole through reduction in environmental impact, improvement in safety, cost savings and time savings.

Digital technologies integrated into the tourism industry include a wide range of:

1. Social media and messengers;
2. Smart mobile apps;
3. Portable IoT systems;
4. Artificial Intelligence and its diverse applications;
5. Augmented reality and virtual reality;
6. "Blockchain," a public registry in which transactions between two users belonging to the same network are stored in a secure, verifiable and persistent manner.
7. Voice technologies;
8. Robotics.

The travel experience is enhanced by personalization, contextual knowledge and real-time monitoring. The Internet of Things is already a critical element of the travel service, providing a "seamless" vacation experience, i.e. hotel, car reservation, flight, and transfer are able to exchange data with each other. Such an approach

minimizes many problems (lack of parking spaces, loss of orientation in unfamiliar areas), and also reduces to a minimum all kinds of expectations of the tourist during the rest.

Another promising area of development is robotization in tourism. Robot-guide technologies are becoming increasingly sophisticated, capable of understanding people and performing tasks based on those needs. Cleaning robots have been widely adopted, reducing the need for personnel. Speech technologies, based on digital speech recognition, have the potential to optimize many operations. It is expected that even small businesses will be able to provide 24/7 service to all their customers by eliminating language barriers in communication.

Blockchain technology provides reliability for orders, reservations, and payment security, and is a foundational element of the digital environment.

Artificial intelligence applications in the field of tourism encompass a range of innovative technologies, including biometric identification, meal planning, and voice search for information. Among the most promising recent developments in this area are augmented reality (AR) apps from companies such as Appinventiv, SeaMonster, and Skignz, which have the potential to significantly enhance the tourism experience.

The use of augmented reality in mobile travel apps allows for the rapid engagement of customers through the incorporation of interactivity, thereby facilitating an immersive user experience and a rich, visually appealing one.

Social media, content marketing and portable IoT systems will need to be integrated into travel apps to handle big data IoT. This will enable innovative and efficient technology to take advantage of new forms of real-time data and provide improved travel services.

In alignment with the State Program for the implementation of the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2026, designated as the "Year of Human Interests and Mahalla Development," as outlined in the Presidential Decree dated January 28, 2022 (№ PD-60), as well as in order to further enhance

accessibility for individuals with disabilities to our country's tourism infrastructure in a comfortable manner, several key initiatives have been identified and are currently being addressed:

1. The key areas of focus for the advancement of barrier-free tourism infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

2. The establishment of prerequisites for the unhindered movement of individuals with disabilities at tourist attractions, cultural institutions, and sites of cultural significance, including museums, theaters, and lodging facilities, is a crucial undertaking;

3. It is of great significance to disseminate information concerning the existence of opportunities for persons with disabilities to travel unhindered across the country. This can be effectively achieved by providing comprehensive explanations of the possibilities that are currently available in our country;

4. Further improvement of the quality of services provided for persons with disabilities at the facilities of the tourism industry, using the capabilities of modern information and communication technologies.

Financing of these activities is made at the expense of the Tourism Support Fund, namely until January 1, 2027 at the expense of the Tourism Support Fund are covered:

a) 50 percent, but not more than 500 thousand soums, of the costs of traveling in Uzbekistan for one thousand people with disabilities of group I and II in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent;

b) 50 percent of the costs of training courses for sign language assistants for people with disabilities who have lost their hearing .

Dynamic Bundling - This is a new technology for shaping and selling a travel product by directly accessing the resource systems of airlines, hotels. To better understand what is dynamic tour packages, let's understand the details, because there are two concepts that are actively used now, which seem to be equivalent to many: dynamic pricing for tours and dynamic tour bundling. Dynamic pricing is more

applicable to classic package tours, which tour operators are trying to bring to the market from offline to online.

This is done by creating databases of tours, using their own software development or industry programs. Dynamic tour bundling involves the formation of a tour package and price determination at the time of sending a request to the reservation systems. After filling in the fields of departure/arrival points and dates on the website, a request is submitted to the airline and hotel reservation system, availability and prices are checked, and the user is provided with options, starting with the minimum price. Having selected the desired option, the user makes a reservation and after payment is instantly received the supporting documents: an electronic air ticket receipt and a hotel accommodation voucher.

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